

**TECHNICAL REPORT
INDUSTRIAL FINAL PROJECT
MMT32510**

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Report Number : UNIMAP/FKTM/P3/221541902	
Project Title: VEHICLE INSPECTION & EVALUATION: USED VEHICLE QUALITY INSPECTION PROCEDURES AND STANDART AT CARSOME	

DECLARATION STATEMENT FORM

Declaration by Student

I, hereby declare that the information provided in all documents prepared and submitted to the university is valid and genuine to the best of my knowledge and belief. I have ensured as a custodian of the confidentiality of all information, data, documents, and any other records that are within my knowledge while undergoing my industrial training, I did not participate in any ways to disclose, prepare, print, publish, distribute or share any such matter with any party whether electronically, physically or in any other manner without permission from the company.

Student Name : MOHAMAD AIMAN AFFENDI BIN MOHAD 'FEDDER
Matric Number : 221541903
Date : 23 September 2025

Signature of Student

Declaration by Industrial Coach

I, hereby verify that the information contained in all documents prepared and submitted by the student is genuine and doesn't contain any confidential information or classified data that might in a way, or another abuse the company's policies, to the best of my knowledge and belief.

Industrial Coach Name	: MUHAMAD SAHRUL NIZAM BIN ZAKWAN
Company Name	: CARSOME EXPERIENCE CENTERS IPOH
Date	: 23 September 2025
	Signature of Industrial Coach

CARSOME
CARSOME SDN BHD (201401025864)
(1101954-M)
Lot 1 & 3, Taman Tasek Indra,
2 Laluan Tasek Timur 5,
31400 Ipoh.

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1 EXTENDED ABSTRACT

This Final Year Project (FYP) investigates the optimization of the vehicle inspection process at CARSOME, Southeast Asia's largest automotive e-commerce platform, by focusing on reducing the number of non-essential inspection points. The existing inspection process consists of 251 points, which has resulted in significant delays, inspector fatigue, and extended customer wait times, negatively impacting overall customer satisfaction. The main objective of this project is to streamline the inspection process by eliminating redundant and non-critical inspection points, thus improving the efficiency of the service without compromising the accuracy and quality of vehicle assessments. A comprehensive survey was conducted with key personnel at CARSOME, including Quality Control Officers, Retail Managers, and Assistant Retail Managers. The feedback indicated that certain inspection points, such as minor cosmetic details and components that do not directly affect the vehicle's safety or performance, could be excluded from the inspection process. For example, checks on minor scratches, non-functional interior electronics, and non critical fluid levels were deprioritized, allowing inspectors to focus on key safety and performance aspects of the vehicle. The implementation of this optimized inspection process resulted in a significant reduction in inspection time. The total time taken for vehicle inspection was reduced by approximately 18 minutes, improving operational efficiency and reducing the workload on inspectors. This time savings directly translated into shorter customer wait times, improving the overall customer experience. The project also highlighted a reduction in inspector fatigue, as the more focused and streamlined process allowed inspectors to work more efficiently without unnecessary strain.

Keywords

Vehicle Inspection, Process Optimization, Operational Efficiency, Customer Satisfaction, Inspector Fatigue, CARSOME.

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2 INTRODUCTION

Figure 2.1:- CARSOME Ipoh Experience Center

Southeast Asia's largest integrated automotive e-commerce platform is called CARSOME. The founder of CARSOME is Eric Cheng back in 2015 aiming to digitalize the used car market in the region by improving the buying and selling experience and having a presence in Malaysia, Indonesia, Thailand, and Singapore. The process covers everything from vehicle inspection to ownership transfer and financing, ensuring a smooth experience from start to finish. CARSOME offers end-to-end solutions to customers and used car dealers, guaranteeing dependable, practical, and effective service. Figure 2.1 shows CARSOME experience center branch in Ipoh.[1]

CARSOME's platform offers a transparent, efficient, and hassle-free process for customers looking to sell their cars. Through its extensive network of inspection centers, CARSOME provides a comprehensive vehicle inspection service that evaluates key aspects of a vehicle's condition, including mechanical, exterior, and interior components. This inspection data is used to offer competitive pricing, ensuring that sellers receive fair value for their vehicles. As an end to-end platform, CARSOME handles every aspect of the car transaction process, including inspection, valuation, ownership transfer, and financing, making it a one-stop solution for customers.[1]

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The inspection in CARSOME is an important tool for guaranteeing the quality of cars. It gives inspectors a thorough checklist that covers the engine, undercarriage, exterior, and interior among them other aspects of the vehicle. Inspectors make sure no detail is missed by methodically recording each component's condition using the app. CARSOME has more than 80 centers across more than 50 cities.[1]

Inspectors can also take direct pictures and videos of the car using the app, which gives them visual proof of any problems or damage. The inspection process is kept more transparent because of this documentation. The current inspection app contains total of 251 inspection point in the current inspection app that need to be inspected. Many inspectors at CARSOME experience center Ipoh have complained that the current inspection points are too numerous, leading to longer inspection times and extended waiting hours for customers.

The inspection delays are extremely problematic since they have a direct effect on CARSOME's capacity to deliver precise and timely vehicle assessments. It is because, when the inspection delays, surely the waiting duration for customer will be increase, inspectors will be fatigue making inspection on long period for single car and this could effect the reputation of the CARSOME.

The report will start with an Introduction that explains the purpose of the project: to reduce inspection points at CARSOME to make the process faster. It will briefly describe the current challenges with inspection times and outline the main objectives and scope of the project. Next, the Methodology section will explain how the data was collected and analyzed, including steps like reviewing the current inspection process and identifying which inspection points can be reduced or eliminated.

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Following this, the Results and Discussion section will present the findings, showing the impact of reducing inspection points on overall inspection time. It will include feedback from the CARSOME Ipoh experience center top management. Finally, the report will end with a Conclusion and Recommendations section, summarizing the key results and suggesting next steps for CARSOME to fully implement the improved inspection process.

3 PROBLEM STATEMENTS

3.1 Identification of the Problem:-

The current 251 inspection points at CARSOME lead to prolonged inspection duration, affecting operational efficiency and increasing customer wait times. Inspectors end up taking longer than necessary to complete each inspection as a result, which makes the car to pending for long time. Total of 251 inspection points seems to be the problem for this inspection to be done for long time cause vehicle to be queue for a long time and. Figure 3.1 shows inspection process carry on by inspector and Figure 3.2 shows pending cars that parked for their turn to be inspected.

Figure 3.1: Inspection Process

Figure 3.2 Pending Cars

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Inspectors become fatigued more quickly as a result of the inspection application's inefficiencies and prolonged use. This affects their general job satisfaction and well being in addition to their capacity to conduct exhaustive and accurate inspections. Figure 3.3 shows the fatigued inspector keep seeing the time while making inspection.

Figure 3.3 Fatigued Inspector

More inspection points lead to longer durations and increased wait times for customers, which can result in dissatisfaction, negative reviews, and potential loss of business as customers seek faster services. Figure 3.4 shows customers are waiting to be done inspection for their car. Figure 3.5 shows negative reviews by customers because of the waiting period they faced.

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Very bad customer service, I booked an appointment for 11:30, got there at 11:20 After taking keys and registration I was asked to sign a form, after that told to wait Waited for 30 mins, went to ask how long till my car will be processed and they said 2 hours!!! What's the point of appointments if you can't honor them

 2

Really bad experience here. Appointment at 4.30pm I was there about 10mins earlier. They told me there is a delay. My slot is 5.15pm. I was still alright. Took about 45mins for inspection and then came the worst part. The offer price. Just ... [More](#)

Figure 3.4 Bad Customer Review

3.2 Significance of the Problem:

This problem is important to study and understand because it directly hit CARSOME reputation. Those below has listed the significance of the problem:

- Operational Efficiency: Operational efficiency can be greatly increased by addressing the inefficiencies in the inspection application.
- Inspector Well-Being: By shortening inspection times and streamlining the application, inspector fatigue can be reduced, improving performance and job satisfaction. Additionally, this can lower attrition rates and enhance inspectors' working condition.
- Customer Satisfaction: Lower waiting times for customers will result in happier customers. Customer loyalty and goodwill are promoted by satisfied customers, who are more likely to use CARSOME again in the future and refer the company to others.
- Reputation and Trust: CARSOME's standing as a reliable and competent service provider will grow if the inspection procedure is made more effective and reliable. This could improve CARSOME's standing in the competitive industry and draw more clients.

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4 OBJECTIVES

- To improve the efficiency of CARSOME's vehicle inspection process by refining inspection points and reducing inspection time, while maintaining safety and quality. The goal is to lessen inspector fatigue, enhance customer satisfaction, and boost operational productivity.
- Identify and eliminate non-essential inspection points that do not impact vehicle safety or performance.
- Decrease the total vehicle inspection time to less than 40 minutes.
- Improve customer satisfaction by reducing waiting times, with the goal of having most customers satisfied with the wait times after the changes are implemented.

5 SCOPES

- The scope of this report is to identify and eliminate non-critical inspection points to shorten the overall vehicle inspection process at CARSOME.
- The focus is on optimizing critical safety and performance-related checks, reducing inspector fatigue, and improving customer satisfaction by delivering timely inspections, thus enhancing CARSOME's reputation and operational productivity.
- One limitation of the study is that the testing was conducted outside working hours to avoid disturbing ongoing inspections, which may not reflect typical operational conditions.
- Additionally, the test was performed on a single vehicle (PERODUA MYVI), which may limit the applicability of the findings across other vehicle models.

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6 METHODOLOGY / WORK PROCEDURE

6.1 Inspection Points

This Final Year Project (FYP) report's general layout is set up to methodically handle the issue of extended inspection times brought on by the CARSOME inspection application. CARSOME has total of 251 inspection points that need to be carry on that includes, Interior, Exterior, Test Drive and Undercarriage of the vehicle. Figure 6.1 until 6.8 shows the inspection point of every part of the vehicle. Figures 6.1 until 6.8 show the inspection point of the vehicle that need to be inspected. There are total of 251 points that should be inspected and mention every single of it weather the section is pass or not.

View Inspection Report: # [REDACTED]	
General Info	
Year	2013
Brand	Perodua
Model	Myvi
Variant	1.5 Extreme Hatchback (FWD)
Engine	1.5
Transmission	Auto
Offered Price	16900
Reserve Price	552391U
License Plate Number	R31A77J
Engine No	PM2M6035002084201
Chassis No	Petrol
Fuel Type	30/09/2013
Registration Date	08/04/2025
Road Tax Expiry	Yellow
Original Color	Yellow
Current Color	5
Seat	Private
Registration Type	151379
Current Mileage	Yes
License Plate?	Yes
Existing Loan	Yes
Spore Key	Yes
Road Test	
Transmission, Transaxle & Clutch	
Transmission / Transaxle Shift	Shifting Delays
Transmission / Transaxle Noise	Passed
Shift Interlock Operation	Passed
Drive Axle / Transfer Case Noise	N/A
Clutch Operation	N/A
Steering & Brake	
Steering Operation	Excessive Free Play,Vibrate
Undercarriage Noise	

Figure 6.1 Inspection Points

Knocking Noise: When On Uneven Road,Knocking	
Noise When Turning	
ABS Operation	Passed
Brake Operation	Spongy
Engine	
Engine Starting	Passed
Engine Idling	Vibrates
Engine Acceleration	Passed
Engine Noise	Passed
Exterior	
Body Panels & Bumpers	
Right Front Door	Scratched
Right Front Fender	Paint Peel Out,Scratched
Accident Vehicle Front Right	Passed
Flood Ridden Front Right	Passed
Cut & Joint Vehicle Front Right	Passed
Front Right Construction Use/off road	Passed
Right Rear Door	Paint Peel Out,Scratched
Right Rear Fender	Scratched,Dented,Repaired,Repaint
Rear Right Fender Glass	N/A
Accident Vehicle Rear Right	Passed
Flood Ridden Rear Right	Passed
Cut & Joint Vehicle Rear Right	Passed
Rear Right Construction Use/off road	Passed
Accident Vehicle Rear	Moderate
Flood Ridden Rear	Passed
Cut & Joint Vehicle Rear	Passed
Back Construction Use/off road	Passed
Rear Bonnet	Scratched,Replaced,Repaint
Rear Bumper	Not
	Align,Scratched,Repaired,Repaint,Replaced,Dented
Left Rear Door	Dented,Scratched
Left Rear Fender	Scratched,Repaired,Repaint
Rear Left Fender Glass	N/A
Accident Vehicle Rear Left	Passed
Flood Ridden Rear Left	Passed
Cut & Joint Vehicle Rear Left	Passed
Rear Left Construction Use/off road	Passed
Left Front Door	Scratched,Dented
Left Front Fender	Dented,Scratched
Accident Vehicle Front Left	Passed

Figure 6.2 Inspection Points

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Flood Ridden Front Left	Passed
Cut & Joint Vehicle Front Left	Passed
Front Left Construction Use/off road	Passed
Front Bumper	Scratched,Repaired,Repaint
Front Bonnet	Scratched,Repaired,Repaint
Front Bonnet Support	Passed
Front Bonnet Insulator	Passed
Emblem	Passed
Chassis or Engine Number Tampered	Passed
Front Construction Use/off road	Passed
Accident Vehicle Front	Passed
Flood Ridden Front	Passed
Cut & Joint Vehicle Front	Passed
Doors, Hood & Boot	
Roof	Scratched
Spoiler	Paint Faded,Scratched
Rear Bonnet Release Mechanism	Passed
Front Grille	Passed
Front Bonnet Release Mechanism	Passed
Glass & Outside Mirrors	
Front Right Electric Folding Mirror	Passed
Front Right Window	Passed
Right Side Mirror	Scratched
Rear Right Window	Passed
Rear Wipers	Abnormal Noise
Rear Window/Tailgate Glass	Passed
Rear Left Window	Passed
Front Left Electric Folding Mirror	Passed
Front Left Window	Passed
Left Side Mirror	Scratched
Front Wipers	Abnormal Noise
Front Windshield	Stone Chip(s)
Exterior Lights	
Auto On/Off Lights	N/A
Turn Signal Lamp Front Right	Passed
Front Right Headlamp	Cracked,Scratched,Yellowish
Front Right Fog Lamp / Day Time Running Light	Scratched
Reverse Light	Passed
Turn Signal Lamp Rear Right	Passed
Hazard Lights Rear Right	Passed
Taillamp Rear Right	Cracked,Scratched
Turn Signal Lamp Rear Left	Passed

Figure 6.3 Inspection Points

Hazard Lights Rear Left	Passed
Taillamp Rear Left	Cracked,Scratched
Turn Signal Lamp Front Left	Passed
Front Left Headlamp	Cracked,Scratched,Yellowish
Front Left Fog Lamp / Day Time Running Light	Malfunction,Cracked,Scratched,Damaged
Rims, Tires & Wheels	
Front Right Wheel Cover & Center Cap	Passed
Front Right Rim Condition	Scratched
Front Right Tire Condition	Pressure Low,Worn Unevenly
Rear Right Wheel Cover & Center Cap	Passed
Rear Right Rim Condition	Passed
Rear Right Tire Condition	Passed
Rear Left Wheel Cover & Center Cap	Passed
Rear Left Rim Condition	Scratched
Rear Left Tire Condition	Passed
Front Left Wheel Cover & Center Cap	Passed
Front Left Rim Condition	Scratched
Front Left Tire Condition	Pressure Low
Interior	
Safety Belts	
Safety Belts Front Right	Worn out
Safety Belts 2nd Row Right	Passed
Safety Belts 3rd Row Right	N/A
Safety Belts 2nd Row Left	Passed
Safety Belts 3rd Row Left	N/A
Safety Belts Front Left	Passed
Audio & Alarm Systems	
Alarm/Theft-deterent System	Passed
Antenna	Broken
Audio/Monitor Player	Passed
Speaker Front Right	Passed
Speaker 2nd Row Right	Passed
Speaker 3rd Row Right	N/A
Speaker 2nd Row Left	Passed
Speaker 3rd Row Left	N/A
Speaker Front Left	N/A
Reverse Camera	N/A
Dashboard Camera	N/A

Figure 6.4 Inspection Points

Heat, Vent, AC, Defog & Defrost	
Air Conditioning Switch Panel	Passed
Defog/Defrost	Passed
Air Conditioning System	Passed
Front Right Aircond Vents	Loose
A/C blower	Passed
Rear Right Aircond Vents	N/A
Rear Center Aircond Vents	N/A
3rd Row Right Aircond Vents	N/A
Rear Left Aircond Vents	N/A
3rd Row Left Aircond Vents	N/A
Front Left Aircond Vents	Passed
Interior Amenities	
Steering Wheel	Worn Out
Steering Column Lock	Passed
Horn	Passed
Paddle Shifters	N/A
Windshield Wipers Switch	Passed
Washers Switch	Passed
Cruise Control Operation	N/A
Multifunction Steering Wheel Switches	Passed
Meter & Gauges Operation	Passed
Tripmeter & Odometer	Passed
Warning Light	Passed
Indicator Lights	Passed
Instrument Cluster	Passed
Interior Courtesy, Dome & Map Lights	Passed
Sun Visors, Vanity Mirror & Light	Passed
Rear view Mirrors	Passed
Clock	N/A
Multi function display	Passed
Power Outlets	N/A
Cigarette Lighter	N/A
Ashtrays	N/A
Gear knob	Loose
Center Armrest/Console	N/A
i-Drive System	N/A
Handbrake/Footbrake Lever	Passed
Driver/Memory Profile Systems	N/A
Back Parking Sensors / Camera	Passed
Rear Right Memory Profile Systems	Passed
Rear Left Memory Profile Systems	Passed
Passenger Memory Profile Systems	N/A
Front Parking Sensors / Camera	Passed
Power Steering	Passed

Figure 6.5 Inspection Points

Carpet, Trim & Mats	
Dashboard Front Right	Faded,Scratched
Headlining Front Right	Passed
Cooled Seats Front Right	N/A
Heated Seats Front Right	N/A
Driver Seat	Worn Out
Front Right Door Trim & Door Panels	Scratched
Interior Carpet Front Right	Dirty
Floor Mats Front Right	Passed
Right A-Pillar Trim	Passed
Right B-Pillar Trim	Passed
Rear Right Door Trim & Door Panels	Scratched
Headlining 2nd Row Right	Dirty
Rear Seat 2nd Row	Worn out
Front Passenger Seat	Worn Out
Folding Seats	Passed
Interior Carpet 2nd Row Right	Passed
Floor Mats 2nd Row Right	Passed
3rd Row Rear Right Memory Profile Systems	N/A
3rd Row Seat	N/A
Parcel Shelf/Speaker Board	Passed
Headlining 3rd Row Right	N/A
Interior Carpet 3rd Row Right	N/A
Floor Mats 3rd Row Right	N/A
Right C-Pillar Trim	Passed
Luggage Board mats	Passed
Interior Carpet Bonnet	Passed
Rear Left Door Trim & Door Panels	Scratched
Headlining 2nd Row Left	Passed
Interior Carpet 2nd Row Left	Passed
Floor Mats 2nd Row Left	Passed
3rd Row Rear Left Memory Profile Systems	N/A
Headlining 3rd Row Left	N/A
Interior Carpet 3rd Row Left	N/A
Floor Mats 3rd Row Left	N/A
Left C-Pillar Trim	Passed
Dashboard Front Left	Faded,Scratched
Glove box	Loose,Scratched
Headlining Front Left	Passed
Cooled Seats Front Left	N/A
Heated Seats Front Left	N/A
Front Left Door Trim & Door Panels	Scratched
Interior Carpet Front Left	Passed
Floor Mats Front Left	Passed
Left A-Pillar Trim	Passed
Left B-Pillar Trim	Passed

Figure 6.6 Inspection Points

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Sunroof, Moonroof, Convertible Top	
Sunroof/Moonroof	N/A
Convertible Top	N/A
Sunshade / Rear roller blind motor	N/A
Windows & Door Locks	
Remote Entry System	Passed
Keyless/Door Entry System	N/A
Push-Button Start System	N/A
Central Locking System	Passed
Front Right Power Window Controls	Passed
Remote Boot Release	N/A
Fuel Cap Release	Passed
Rear Right Power Window Controls	Passed
Rear Left Power Window Controls	Passed
Front Left Power Window Controls	Passed
Luggage Compartment	
Spare Tyre Sidewall	Passed
Spare Tyre Thread	Passed
Vehicle Jack & ToolKit	Passed
Luggage Compartment Trim	Scratched
Cargo Net	N/A
Luggage Compartment Light	N/A
Undercarriage	
Engine	
Belts	Abnormal Noise
Engine Mounts	Passed
Fluids	
Engine Oil	Major Leaking
Coolant	Passed
Transmission/Transaxle Automatic Fluids	Passed
Power Steering Fluids	N/A
Windshield Washer Fluids	Passed
Brake Fluids	Passed
Cooling System	

Radiator Cap	Passed
Radiator	Passed
Coolant Reservoir Tank	Passed
Cooling Fans	Abnormal Noise
Hoses, Lines & Fittings (Cooling System)	Passed
Electrical System	
Battery	Passed
Starter Operation	Passed
Exhaust System	
Exhaust Muffler	Passed
Splash Cover	Broken
Transmission, Transaxle & Differential	
Transmission Mounts	Passed
Steering and Alignment	
Power Steering Pump	Passed
Rack-and-Pinion, Linkage & Boots	Passed
Brakes	
Front Right Brake Pads	Passed
Rear Right Brake Pads	N/A
Rear Left Brake Pads	N/A
Front Left Brake Pads	Passed
Brake Lines, Hoses & Fittings	Passed
Suspension	
Shock Absorber Front Right	Passed
Shock Absorber Rear Right	Passed
Shock Absorber Rear Left	Passed
Shock Absorber Front Left	Passed

Figure 6.7 Inspection Points

Figure 6.8 Inspection Points

The vehicle inspection at CARSOME involves 251 points that cover all critical aspects of a car, ensuring a comprehensive evaluation of its condition. The exterior inspection assesses the body for damage such as scratches, dents, and signs of previous accidents or flood exposure. It also includes checking lights, windows, mirrors, and tire conditions, including tread depth and rim health. The interior inspection focuses on the functionality of safety systems like airbags and seat belts, while also checking the state of the upholstery, dashboard, and electronics like radios and air conditioning. The undercarriage inspection involves checking the exhaust system, suspension, brake pads, and essential fluids such as engine oil and coolant, with minor fluids like windshield washer fluid sometimes being deprioritized. Finally, the test drive assesses the car's engine performance, braking, transmission, and steering. These inspections ensure the car's safety and roadworthiness while identifying any mechanical or aesthetic issues that may affect its value or functionality.

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6.2 Reason For Inspection Points Exclusion

To improve inspection efficiency and reduce customer wait times at CARSOME, certain inspection points could potentially be excluded or streamlined. Here are some inspection points that might be considered for exclusion or reduction in detail:-

I. Non-Critical Interior Features

- Reason: Features such as seat upholstery condition, minor stains, non-functional electronics (such as a clock or radio), and interior carpets do not significantly affect vehicle performance or safety.
- Justification: These features are aesthetic rather than functional and do not impact the vehicle's roadworthiness. Reducing inspection time spent on these points allows inspectors to focus on critical safety aspects. Additionally, minor cosmetic flaws are generally acceptable to buyers, especially in used cars, where they are expected as part of wear and tear.
- Example: Inspecting minor interior wear such as small scratches or floor mat conditions can be skipped without affecting the customer's trust in the vehicle's mechanical reliability. Total of 5 to 7 minutes can be saved by deducting it.

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II. Minor Fluid Checks

- Reason: Fluids like windshield washer fluid, brake fluid (if not at a critical level), and power steering fluid do not require immediate attention unless they directly impact the vehicle's safety.
- Justification: Most minor fluid levels can be quickly topped up if necessary and don't pose an immediate risk to vehicle performance. By skipping these minor checks, time can be saved, especially since most buyers expect to maintain these fluids regularly as part of ongoing car maintenance.
- Example: Focusing on critical fluids like engine oil and coolant is more important for the safety and performance of the vehicle, while skipping windshield washer fluid checks does not compromise overall vehicle safety. Total of 3 to 5 minutes can be saved by deducting it.

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III. Tire Tread Depth And Rim

- Reason: Detailed checks on all four tires for tread depth and rim condition can be excessive if the tires are visibly in good condition.
- Justification: Visual checks of one or two tires can be sufficient in most cases, especially if the tires are fairly new. More detailed inspections (like tread depth measurement on all tires) can be reserved for cases where there are visible signs of wear or concern. This allows inspectors to save time without compromising safety.
- Example: Inspecting only one tire for tread depth when all tires appear visually new or in good condition reduces inspection time but still ensures road safety. By reducing these checks to one or two tires, the inspection time can be shortened by approximately 3 to 4 minutes, as less time is spent measuring tread depth and inspecting rims in detail.

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IV. Non-Critical Light Checks

- Reason: Lights such as fog lamps, interior cabin lights, or non-essential exterior lights (e.g., parking lights) are not critical to the vehicle's immediate operation.
- Justification: These lights can be deprioritized as they do not directly affect the vehicle's safety or performance. Critical lights such as headlights, brake lights, and turn signals should still be inspected to ensure road safety. Skipping non-critical lights saves time without impacting the vehicle's operational reliability.
- Example: Inspecting interior cabin lights or fog lamps, which have limited usage and are not essential for daily driving, can be skipped without affecting vehicle safety. Skipping the inspection of these non-essential lights could save approximately 2 to 3 minutes during the overall inspection process.

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V. Accessory And Non Essential Features Checks

- Reason: Items like floor mats, trunk organizers, and minor vehicle accessories are not essential to the vehicle's functionality or safety.
- Justification: These accessories do not impact the performance of the vehicle and are often considered add-ons. Skipping the inspection of such items allows inspectors to focus on key performance areas of the vehicle. Moreover, if these accessories are missing or damaged, they can easily be replaced by the buyer or seller without affecting the vehicle's resale value.
- Example: Inspecting or noting the condition of floor mats or trunk organizers is unnecessary for vehicle safety and skipping them streamlines the process without any negative repercussions. By skipping these accessory checks, inspectors can save approximately 1 to 2 minutes.

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VI. Wear and Tear Components

- Reason: Components such as brake pads, hoses, and minor parts that wear out over time typically do not pose immediate risks to the vehicle's operation at the point of sale.
- Justification: These components are part of regular maintenance schedules, and excluding them from the standard inspection won't significantly affect the vehicle's safety. Buyers and sellers usually anticipate these parts will need eventual replacement as part of routine maintenance, making them less critical during initial inspections.
- Example: Excluding detailed brake pad wear checks, especially if the vehicle has not shown performance issues, can reduce 4 to 6 inspection time without compromising short-term vehicle safety.

VII. Emblem Checks And Minor Cosmetic Details

- Reason: Emblems, logos, and minor scratches on the exterior of the car do not affect vehicle performance or safety.
- Justification: These are purely cosmetic issues that can be easily fixed or ignored by both buyers and sellers. Focusing on more significant exterior damage, such as dents or structural issues, is more relevant. Skipping checks on emblems or small cosmetic issues can significantly reduce the overall inspection time.
- Example: An emblem being scratched or missing does not affect vehicle functionality and skipping this check contributes to a more efficient process and saves 2 to 3 minutes.

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6.3 Data Collection Method

Ishikawa Diagram

Figure 6.9 shows the Ishikawa diagram, is a tool used to identify and visually represent the root causes of a specific issue. In this case, it helps to analyse the various factors contributing to delays in the vehicle inspection process at CARSOME, such as inspector fatigue, redundant checks, and time pressure. By categorising these issues, the diagram allows for a clear understanding of the problem, guiding us to develop targeted solutions to streamline the process and improve efficiency.[10]

Figure 6. 9 Ishikawa Diagram

By analyzing the inspection process with this Ishikawa diagram, several non-critical points in the process can be identified for exclusion. For example:-

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- Non-critical checks such as, minor scratches, uncritical light inspections, minor fluids, wear andtear should be deprioritized.
- Inspector fatigue, as identified in the Manpower category, can be reduced by excluding redundant checks.
- Time spent on documentation for non-critical issues can be minimized, ensuring inspectors focus on major components like safety-related parts.

The Ishikawa diagram highlights key factors contributing to inspector fatigue, such as the high number of inspection points and redundant tasks. By addressing these issues, CARSOME can reduce unnecessary checks, allowing inspectors to focus on critical areas, which will lower fatigue, improve efficiency, reduce errors, and enhance customer satisfaction.

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Questions and Surveys

The purpose of the surveys and questionnaires is to collect numerical information from Quality Control Officer, Assistant Retail Manager and Retail Manager. There are total of 4 respondents in this survey they are, Quality Control Officer, 2 Assistant Retail Managers and Retail Manager. This survey has been proposed with the excluded points that want to be excluded and to get approval from top management with reasons on why can be excluded as shown in Discussion Section. Figure 6.10 shows the survey made for top management in CARSOME Ipoh Experience Center.

INSPECTION POINT THAT CAN BE EXCLUDED

I AM MOHAMAD AIMAN AFFENDI BIN MOHAD 'FEDDER FROM UNIVERSITI MALAYSIA PERLIS (UniMAP).THIS FORM IS FOR MY FINAL YEAR PROJECT TO ANALYSE THE INSPECTION POINT THAT CAN EXCLUDED TO MAKE THE INSPECTION PROCESS MORE FASTER. I KINDLY APPRECIATE YOUR TIME TO ANSWER THE SURVEY.

* Indicates required question

WORK ROLE *

Quality Control

Assistance Retail Manager

Retail Manager

Figure 6.10 Survey Form

CARSOME	VEHICLE INSPECTION & EVALUATION: USED VEHICLE QUALITY INSPECTION PROCEDURES AND STANDART AT CARSOME	Report Number:	UNIMAP/FKTM/P1/221541902			
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Figure 6.11 shows the data from survey by Quality Control Officer, Assistant Retail Manager and Retail Manager when all of them agree to exclude the Exterior points in this survey that want to be implemented. Exterior points like minor scratches, emblem checks, and non-critical fluid levels were excluded based on feedback from management, as they do not significantly affect vehicle safety or resale value. Tire depth and tread, emblem, wipers and fog lamps inspection can be skipped because it can also noticed while taking basic photos.

No.	Details	Respondents	Respondent details
1.	Count of emblem	4	Quality Control Officer, 2 Assistant Retail Manager, Retail Manager
2.	Count of front wipers	4	
3.	Count of turn signal lamp front right	4	
4.	Count of front right fog lamp	4	
5.	Count of turn signal lamp front left	4	
6.	Count of front left fog lamp	4	
7.	Count of front right wheel cover & center cap	4	
8.	Count of front right rim condition	4	
9.	Count of front right tire condition	4	
10.	Count of rear right wheel cover & center cap	4	
11.	Count of rear right rim condition	4	
12.	Count of rear right tire condition	4	
13.	Count of front left wheel cover & center cap	4	
14.	Count of front left rim condition	4	
15.	Count of front left tire condition	4	
16.	Count of rear left wheel cover & center cap	4	
17.	Count of rear left rim condition	4	
18.	Count of rear left tire condition	4	

Figure 6.11 Chart Of Exclude Exterior Points

CARSOME	VEHICLE INSPECTION & EVALUATION: USED VEHICLE QUALITY INSPECTION PROCEDURES AND STANDART AT CARSOME	Report Number:	UNIMAP/FKTM/P1/221541902		
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Figure 6.12 shows the data from survey by Quality Control Officer, Assistant Retail Manager and Retail Manager when all of them agree to exclude the Interior points in this survey that I want to implement. The excluded interior points was the cosmetics, wear and tear and not important interior features, as mentioned before because it will not affect the performance of the vehicle.

No.	Details	Respondents	Respondent details
1.	Count of safety belts <u>3nd</u> row right	4	Quality Control Officer, 2 Assistant Retail Manager, Retail Manager
2.	Count of safety belts <u>3nd</u> row left	4	
3.	Count of antenna	4	
4.	Count of clock	4	
5.	Count of interior carpet front right	4	
6.	Count of floor mats front right	4	
7.	Count of interior carpet <u>2nd</u> row right	4	
8.	Count of floor mats <u>2nd</u> row right	4	
9.	Count of interior carpet <u>nd</u> row right	4	
10.	Count of floor mats <u>3nd</u> row right	4	
11.	Count of interior carpet <u>2nd</u> row left	4	
12.	Count of floor mats <u>2nd</u> row left	4	
13.	Count of interior carpet <u>3nd</u> row left	4	
14.	Count of floor mats <u>3nd</u> row left	4	
15.	Count of interior carpet front left	4	
16.	Count of floor mats front left	4	
17.	Count of spare tyre sidewall	4	
18.	Count of spare tyre thread	4	
19.	Count of vehicle <u>jack&toolkit</u>	4	
20.	Count of luggage compartment trim	4	
21.	Count of cargo net	4	
22.	Count of luggage compartment light	4	

Figure 6.12 Chart Of Exclude Interior Points

CARSOME	VEHICLE INSPECTION & EVALUATION: USED VEHICLE QUALITY INSPECTION PROCEDURES AND STANDART AT CARSOME	Report Number:	UNIMAP/FKTM/P1/221541902			
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Figure 6.13 shows the data from survey by Quality Control Officer, Assistant Retail Manager and Retail Manager when all of them agree to exclude the Undercarriage points in this survey that I want to implement. Minor fluid checks, wear and tear parts such brake pads and hoses will not affect directly the safety and performance of the vehicle.

No.	Details	Respondents	Respondent details
1.	Count of belts	4	Quality Control Officer, 2 Assistant Retail Manager, Retail Manager
2.	Count of power steering fluids	4	
3.	Count of windshield washer fluids	4	
4.	Count of brake fluids	4	
5.	Count of hoses, <u>lines</u> & fittings	4	
6.	Count of front right brake pads	4	
7.	Count of rear right brake pads	4	
8.	Count of front left brake pads	4	
9.	Count of rear left brake pads	4	
10.	Count of brake lines, hoses & fittings	4	

Figure 6.13 Chart Of Exclude Undercarriage Point

All the Figure from 6.11 until 6.13 shows the excluded inspection points that can be made in the approval of all 4 main heads in CARSOME Ipoh Experience Center, they are, Quality Control Officer, two Assistant Retail Manager and Retail Manager. The inspection points identified for elimination to optimize the vehicle inspection process include non-critical interior features such as seat upholstery, minor stains, and non-functional electronics; minor fluid checks like windshield washer fluid and non-critical brake fluid; and detailed tire tread and rim condition checks, which can be reduced to visual inspections. Non-critical light checks, including fog lamps and interior cabin lights, and accessory inspections like floor mats and trunk organizers are also

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deprioritized. Additionally, wear-and-tear components such as brake pads and hoses, along with cosmetic checks on emblems and minor exterior scratches, are excluded.

Figure 6.14 is a survey made for waiting customers in CARSOME Ipoh Experience Center to know about weather they are satisfied or not by the waiting hours. They survey also focus on what is the time that the customers can tolerate while waiting for their car to be inspected.

Waiting Duration In CARSOME For Inspection Process

I AM MOHAMAD AIMAN AFFENDI BIN MOHAD 'FEDDER FROM UNIVERSITI MALAYSIA PERLIS (UniMAP). THIS FORM IS FOR MY FINAL YEAR PROJECT TO ANALYSE THE THE DURATION OF TIME THAT YOU CAN TOLERATE WHILE MAKING AN INSPECTION IN CARSOME. SINCERELY APPRECIATE YOUR TIME TO ANSWER THE QUESTIONS.

Figure 6.14 Survey Form

Total of 41 number of respondent has been gain by this survey. The first question asked was do they feel satisfied with the current waiting duration. Figure 6.15 shows total of 38 customers or 92.7% respondents said that they were not satisfied. It has proven that the waiting duration really cause trouble for the customers.

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Figure 6.15 Satisfaction Survey

To assess the customers' waiting time, a question was asked regarding how long they had to wait for their car to be inspected on the day of the survey. Figure 6.16 shows 20 numbers of respondents said that their car takes more than an hour to be inspected, the other respondents said it takes 50 to 60 minutes to be inspected. It's clear that the inspection in CARSOME takes longer than 50 minutes to be inspected.

Figure 6.16 Identify Inspection Duration

CARSOME	VEHICLE INSPECTION & EVALUATION: USED VEHICLE QUALITY INSPECTION PROCEDURES AND STANDART AT CARSOME	Report Number:		UNIMAP/FKTM/P1/221541902		
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Figure 6.17 shows the duration of waiting period that customers can tolerate while let their car to be inspected. Majority of 73.2% of respondents has stated that, they can tolerate for waiting 30-40 minutes for their car to be inspected. This also has clear that customer satisfaction can be achieved if the inspection can be done within 30-40 minutes.

Figure 6.17 Customers Toleration Duration

Most respondents indicated that they waited more than 50 minutes for their car inspection, which exceeds the tolerable waiting time for the majority of customers. This directly affects customer satisfaction, with longer wait times leading to frustration and negative reviews. Addressing this issue by reducing inspection times would not only improve customer satisfaction but also enhance CARSOME's reputation and operational efficiency. Reducing waiting times can lead to better customer retention, repeat business, and positive word-of-mouth, which are crucial for the company's growth.

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Figure 6.18 illustrates the survey conducted for CARSOME Ipoh Experience Center Inspectors to assess whether they experience fatigue during the inspection process and to evaluate if the exclusion of certain inspection points can help reduce their fatigue levels. The survey aimed to gather feedback from all 10 inspectors on how the current inspection process affects their workload and whether streamlining certain tasks could improve their efficiency and well-being.

Analysis of Fatigue Reduction Strategies in Vehicle Inspection

I am Mohamad Aiman Affendi from UNIVERSITI MALAYSIA PERLIS(UniMAP). This form is for my Final Year Project to analyse the fatigue cause by the inspectors. i kindly appreciate your time to answer survey

Figure 6.18 Survey For Inspectors

CARSOME	VEHICLE INSPECTION & EVALUATION: USED VEHICLE QUALITY INSPECTION PROCEDURES AND STANDART AT CARSOME	Report Number:		UNIMAP/FKTM/P1/221541902		
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The first question asked inspectors if they experienced fatigue due to the 251 inspection points at CARSOME as shown in Figure 6.19. A total of 80% of the inspectors responded "yes," while 20% were unsure. This majority response clearly indicates that the extensive number of inspection points is a significant factor contributing to inspector fatigue.

Figure 6.19 Fatigue Survey

The survey also asked how often inspectors experience physical fatigue during inspections. According to Figure 6.20, 80% reported feeling fatigue several times a day, while the rest said occasionally. This highlights that most inspectors frequently face fatigue during their work.

Figure 6.20 Fatigue Experience Survey

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The next question aimed to determine if inspectors experience a drop in accuracy when feeling fatigued, as shown in Figure 6.21. Most inspectors responded "yes," indicating that fatigue leads to mistakes during inspections. Addressing this issue is important, as errors can negatively impact CARSOME's reputation.

Figure 6.21 Inspection Accuracy Survey

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The final question assessed the effectiveness of reducing fatigue by excluding non-critical inspection points, as shown in Figure 6.22. Most inspectors responded that this would be highly effective. This suggests that eliminating non-critical points could significantly reduce inspector fatigue.

Figure 6.22 Reduction Effectiveness Survey

The significance of the findings from the survey is clear. Most inspectors indicated that the current 251 inspection points lead to fatigue, which frequently impacts their accuracy during inspections. This is a critical issue, as errors in inspections can harm CARSOME's reputation. The survey also shows that eliminating non-critical inspection points could significantly reduce fatigue, allowing inspectors to maintain better focus and accuracy. Implementing these changes could improve the efficiency of inspections, enhance inspector well-being, and help safeguard the company's reputation by reducing mistakes.

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6.4 Materials And Equipment

Google Form

Google form is used in this survey to gain the inspection process that can be excluded while making the inspection. This survey has only been asked to Quality Control Officer, 2 Assistant Retail Manager and Retail Manager. The excluded points been collected in a way when all 4 of them answers to exclude the inspection points.

Excel

Microsoft excel also has been used in this report to make graph on the selected excluded points by all four that answer the survey. This helps me to get a proper data on which points that can be reduced as shown in Figure 6.10, 6.11 and 6.12.

PERODUA

The car has been used to make the inspection is PERODUA. This vehicle is used to make the inspection before and after exclude the inspection points. This procedure made in same vehicle to get the accuracy while record the time.

Stopwatch

For stopwatch Honour X9A 5G model has been used to record the time before and after exclude the inspection points. Like many other modern smartphones, the Honor X9a has a built-in stopwatch function that is accurate for everyday use. Most daily tasks can be completed with the accuracy, which is typically down to milliseconds.

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6.5 Procedural Steps

The flowchart in Figure 6.23 summarizes the key steps taken to optimize the vehicle inspection process at CARSOME Ipoh Experience Center. It shows how the current inspection points were reviewed, non-critical points were identified for removal, and testing was conducted before and after the changes. This helped reduce inspection time while maintaining quality. The flowchart provides a clear overview of the process and how each step contributed to improving efficiency.

Figure 6.23 Procedural Flowchart

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The flowchart effectively represents the methodology by outlining the key steps taken to optimize the vehicle inspection process at CARSOME. It starts by reviewing the existing 251 inspection points, followed by identifying non-critical points based on feedback from surveys and personnel. The current process is then tested to establish a baseline, after which non-essential points are excluded to streamline the inspection. The optimized process is retested using the same conditions, allowing for a direct comparison of time and inspector feedback before and after the changes. Finally, the results are evaluated to determine whether the objective of reducing inspection time while maintaining quality standards was achieved. This structured approach visually simplifies the methodology and demonstrates the logical flow of decisions and their impact on operational efficiency.

7 RESULT

7.1 Time Calculation Before Implement

Before implement the excluded points from the survey, conducted a test by using current inspection points to calculate the duration of the inspection process. This test involved same inspector named Faisal, he is a Certified Inspector and has 3 years of working experience in CARSOME and also used same car for the test. The implement made by just pick PASS on excluded inspection points.

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Test Drive

For test drive, the duration taken to make is 2 minutes and 36 seconds as showed in Figure 7.2. The Test Drive usually make a simple drive around 300 to 500 meters over the CARSOME area. Figure 7.2 shows the test drive process carried out by the inspectors.

Figure 7.1 Test Drive Time

Figure 7.2 Test Drive Process

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Exterior Inspection

For Exterior inspection points it take total of 20 minutes and 37 seconds to make the inspection as shown in Figure 7.3. This takes much time because needs to check for accidents, flood and overall of the exterior points. Figure 7.4 shows the exterior inspection process carried out by inspectors.

Figure 7.3 Exterior Time

Figure 7.4 Exterior Inspection Process

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Interior Inspection

Figure 7.5 shows Interior inspection process that takes 22 minutes and 22 seconds. The minutes over here surely takes a lot of time for the inspection because of the points that need to be inspected such as safety belts, audio player, speaker, air conditioning system and so on. Figure 7.6 shows the inspection process for interior points.

Figure 7.5 Interior Time

Figure 7.6 Interior Inspection Process

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Undercarriage Inspection

For the undercarriage it takes 10 minutes and 4 seconds as shown in Figure 7.7 to make inspection before the implementation. This includes fluids, exhaust system, brakes and others. Figure 7.8 shows the undercarriage inspection process.

Figure 7.7 Undercarriage Time

Figure 7.8 Undercarriage Inspection Process

The overall time taken for the entire inspection process before making the implementation was 55 minutes and 39 seconds by a certified inspector. This surely shows a high amount of time needed to make the inspection with current inspection points.

7.2 After Exclude Inspection Points

The test has made on same day after the closing hour to avoid any disturbance for ongoing Inspection Process. This inspection made by same car and same inspector to make to to get a accurate duration of time.

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Test Drive

For Test Drive there is no any big changes because nothing is excluded from Test Drive inspection. The test drive duration takes 2 minutes and 59 seconds as shows in Figure 7.9. Figure 7.10 also shows the test drive process for inspection. The increased traffic congestion on one of the roadways, which causes slower vehicle movement and lengthier travel times, is reason for the 23-second delay.

Figure 7.9 Test Drive Time

Figure 7.10 Test Drive Inspection Process

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Exterior Inspection

After the implementation, the inspection duration taken for inspection Exterior parts are 15 minutes and 45 seconds as in Figure 7.11. Significance change in time noticed after the implementation of reduced inspection point. Figure 7.12 shows the exterior inspection points.

Figure 7.11 Exterior Time

Figure 7.12 Exterior Inspection Process

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Interior Inspection Point

After the implementation, the inspection duration taken for inspection Interior parts are 14 minutes 57 seconds as in Figure 7.13. This also get a good number in time for done the overall interior inspection. Figure 7.14 shows the interior inspection process.

Figure 7.13 Interior Time

Figure 7.14 Interior Inspection Process

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Undercarriage Inspection

After the implementation, the inspection duration taken for inspect Undercarriage parts is 6 minutes and 27 seconds. This gives a good duration after the cut off. Figure 7.16 shows the undercarriage inspection process.

Figure 7.15 Undercarriage Time

Figure 7.16

Undercarriage Inspection Process

After the implementation, the total time taken to make the inspection is 38 minutes and 8 seconds. This duration surely indicate a good time for making an inspection and reduce inspectors burden and increase customers satisfaction.

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8 DISCUSSION

The result has proofed that excluded inspection points surely can give a faster inspection. The total time taken before making the implementation takes 55 minutes and 39 seconds, this duration surely make a big waiting time for customers to wait and can make them frustrated while waiting for their car to be done inspected. After the exclusion of the inspection point implemented, the recorded time was 38 minutes 08 seconds has been used for inspecting the car. This surely has stated that this time frame has reduced almost 18 minutes and has achieved the customers duration of waiting period that they can tolerate while making an inspection. This will help CARSOME to gain a good reputation among customers, reduce fatigue for inspectors and help the inspectors inspect more cars in a day when the duration of inspection reduced.

A question in survey included to identify weather CARSOME reputation would be damaged if the implementation of reduced inspection points. All the answers from the top management has been recorded to make sure no bad reputation happen to CARSOME. The question wasn't asked to customers because they may not have the technical knowledge to judge which inspection points matter for safety. Instead, top management, who understand the process better, gave their input to ensure that reducing inspection points won't harm CARSOME's reputation.

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Retail Manager

Question

In your point of view, do you think this excluded points won't give any negative impact to CARSOME?

This wont give negative impact because the places i pick excluded such as tyres, brakes, carpets and others are among tear and wear. Parts such Oils checking are also not such important because we can just top up the oils if want to give to other parties.

Figure 8.1 Retail Manager Answer

The statement from Retail Manager has proved that this implementation will not give any bad reputation because the excluded parts were Wear and Tear as shown in Figure 8.1. Even, the steering oil, brake oil and others just can be add on if needed rather than inspecting it.

Quality Control

Question

In your point of view, do you think this excluded points won't give any negative impact to CARSOME?

Tidak sebab bila nk serah kereta kt dealer walaupun inspector tak marking benda seperti tayar, brake pad, minyak, karpet apa smua takkan dpt complaint. Benda yang saya tanda boleh dikurangkan bagi ccepatkan inspection. Mat atau carper jika kotor boleh bersihkan sahaja bila ingin serah kepada dealer lain.

Figure 8.2 Quality Control Officer Answer

The Quality Control Officer also stated that the excluded points that made are the ones that even dealer will not make any complaints even sometimes inspectors missed on it. So, the reduced points can give a faster inspection and will not damage CARSOME reputation. This has been proved in Figure 8.2.

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First Assistant Retail Manager

Question

In your point of view, do you think this excluded points won't give any negative impact to CARSOME?

Benda yang saya tick ialah antara yang saya tidak menilai apabila ingin memberi harga kepada customer. Benda yg penting sy nilai untuk bagi Value ialah tahap accident kereta, flood, cut & joint, paint dan sebagainya. Brek tidak perlu dinalai untuk mempercepatkan inspection dan tidak dinalai semasa memberi harga.

Figure 8.3 First Retail Manager Answer

The first Assistant Retail Manager stated that when he wants to give price to the customer after the inspection, he will not evaluate the following points that he excluded as shown in Figure 8.3. So, it been clear that the excluded points can be reduced because it wont be evaluate when making the price.

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Second Assistant Retail Manager

Question

In your point of view, do you think this excluded points won't give any negative impact to CARSOME?

This has not much effect, bcz when evaluate the price we dont check every single part of the vehicle. Even, to enter B2C to resell to customers we make repairs and service. The selected parts usually dont have much complaints from dealers. Simple repairable things also can be avoided.

Figure 8.4 Second Retail Manager Answer

Figure 8.4 shows the statement from another Assistant Retail Manager has said when he wants to put the car in B2C, they even make repairs or change the excluded parts. B2C is where CARSOME resell the cars on their own platform after repairing it. And he said simple repairable parts just can be avoided to help the inspection process to be more faster.

All those statement has confirmed that CARSOME would not have any bad reputation when they avoid the excluded inspection process. This will help inspectors to make faster inspection and reduce work burden.

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8.1 Recommendation For Future Report Or Practical Applications

- Investigate Collaborations with Tech Founders: Take into account forming alliances with tech firms that specialize in automated inspection and automotive diagnostics. Working together can give you access to modern resources and knowledge, which can speed up the adoption of more effective procedures.
- Install Advanced Diagnostic Tools: CARSOME should make investments in AI-driven analytics and automated inspection systems to make up for the removal of some inspection points. By evaluating vehicle conditions fast and precisely, these tools lessen the need for manual inspections and accelerate the procedure even more.
- Prioritize Critical Inspection Points: Upcoming reports should to concentrate on honing the list of crucial inspection points that have an immediate bearing on the quality and safety of vehicles. CARSOME can maintain this list up to date and optimized in order to guarantee that inspections continue to be thorough but effective. It does this by utilizing data analytics, customer feedback, and industry best practices.

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9 CONCLUSION

The objective of the report has been achieved by reducing the inspection time. The main unnecessary inspection points in CARSOME's vehicle inspection procedure that increase inspection times have been identified in this report. The study shows a possible decrease in overall inspection time without sacrificing the quality of the assessments by optimizing the procedure and concentrating on crucial inspection areas.

The report makes a contribution to the field by outlining a clear methodology for identifying and removing pointless steps and offering a practical approach to optimizing vehicle inspections. This method can be used in other comparable automotive inspection scenarios in addition to CARSOME.

The results have larger implications for CARSOME's efforts to increase customer satisfaction and operational effectiveness. Quicker inspections can improve overall business performance by lowering customer wait times and boosting efficiency for the organization.

This study successfully optimized the vehicle inspection process by reducing inspection points, resulting in faster inspections and improved customer satisfaction. Future research should explore the integration of AI-driven diagnostics to further enhance accuracy and efficiency, making the process even more streamlined and scalable.

To sum up, improving inspection points is an essential first step in raising CARSOME's efficiency. The study shows that mindful improvement of processes can have a big impact and open up new opportunities for growth and innovation in the automotive e-commerce industry.

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10 REFERENCES

1. About Carsome | Sell and Buy Used Cars. (2020). Carsome.my. <https://www.carsome.my/about-us>
2. Author, C. (2021, May 19). Eric Cheng's Road to Success: Failures, Hard Times & Discovering Carsome. Carsome Malaysia. <https://www.carsome.my/news/item/carsome-ceo-eric>
3. How to make an Ishikawa diagram. (2020). Mindmanager.com. <https://www.mindmanager.com/en/features/ishikawa-diagram/#:~:text=An%20Ishikawa%20diagram%20is%20designed,issues%0are%20likely%20to%20arise>.
4. Kirill Tšernov. (2017, December 22). Long Waiting Times Cost You Sales | Qminder. Qminder; Qminder. <https://www.qminder.com/blog/queue-management/long-waiting-times-sales/>
5. Leigh. (2022, July 28). Carsome Review - My Experience Buying and Selling My Car with Carsome. Dividend Magic. <https://dividendmagic.com.my/my-car-with-carsome/>
6. Tools and media. (2021, March 19). What is customer satisfaction? Definition + importance. Zendesk. <https://www.zendesk.com/blog/3-steps-achieving-customer-satisfaction-loyalty/>
7. kaizo. (2021, November 2). The importance of customer satisfaction (+ stats to prove it) - Kaizo. Kaizo. <https://kaizo.com/blog/importance-of-customer-satisfaction/>
8. Million, R. (2024, July 16). Carsome Newsroom. Carsome Newsroom. <https://news.carsome.com/news/carsome-secures-rm100-million-financing-facility-from-ambank-the-largest-bank-backed-facility-for-the-group>

